

Appendix: Reflective Prompts

Appendix to the paper "Mirror, mirror on my search...": Data-Driven Reflection and Experimentation with Search Behaviour" that was accepted to the EC-TEL 2019 as full research paper.

The following Table contains the whole list of reflection prompts that were implemented in the widget. The *feature* represents a placeholder for a feature and is replaced during run-time with a corresponding feature available on the search platform. Also, *number* is a placeholder and will be replaced during run-time with the corresponding number.

Reflective Prompts
<i>Low-level prompt</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>feature</i> is the most used feature on the MOVING platform. Why don't you use also <i>feature</i>? • <i>feature</i> is the most used feature on the MOVING platform. Why do you use this feature that often? • <i>feature</i> is the most used feature on the MOVING platform. What do you like best using this feature? • <i>feature</i> is the most used feature on the MOVING platform. What are the advantages of using this feature? • It seems you like using the <i>feature</i>. You already used it <i>number</i> times. Please try out also <i>feature</i>. • You have not tried the <i>feature</i>. Why haven't you tried it out before? What is the reason why you have not used it? • Tell me about your experience using the <i>feature</i>. • Do you like using the <i>feature</i>? • How satisfied are you while using the <i>feature</i>? • Do you like sorting the search results by date? • Do you like sorting the search results by relevance? • Have you used the <i>feature</i>, because the widget recommended it to you? • Why did you use the <i>feature</i> more than the <i>feature</i>?
<i>Medium-level prompt</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What did you learn by using the <i>feature</i>? • Did using the <i>feature</i> improve your performance. And if yes how? • Did using the <i>feature</i> improve your skills. And if yes how? • The <i>feature</i> is less used than <i>feature</i>, why do you think is this the case? • Did you improve your search behaviour by using the <i>feature</i>? • Which of the features listed above do you find the most useful and why? • Which of the features listed above are you most satisfied with and why?
<i>High-level prompt</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Think about your feature usage. Did you improve search behaviour over time? • Think about your feature usage. Did you change your search behaviour over time? • Did the widget improve your feature usage? • Did the widget change your feature usage? • What feature brought you the most satisfaction and why? • What is your benefit using the <i>feature</i>? • What is your benefit using the sorting of search results by date? • What is your benefit using the sorting of search results by relevance? • Which type of sorting mechanism in the search results did you use and was it helpful for you?